

INFLUENCE OF THE INTERFACE STRENGTH ON LOCAL FAILURE PROCESSES IN FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The damage tolerance of fiber reinforced composites strongly depends on the microscopical failure processes arising at initiation and during propagation of macroscopical failure. In this paper, local failure processes such as fiber break with simultaneous radial cracks followed by debonding are investigated by means of model studies using the finite element method. The model is similar to that of a common fragmentation test. The influence of thermal prestresses as well as of interfacial friction is studied. Furthermore, the fiber type - glass and carbon fiber - and the fiber volume fraction is varied. It is shown that the fiber break releases a large amount of energy and is probably accompanied either by a matrix or an interface crack. Interfacial friction dissipates a large amount of stored strain energy due to radial compressive stresses acting in the interface.

KEYWORDS: interface crack, energy release rate, fracture mechanics, debonding, thermal stresses, friction, finite element method (FEM)

INTRODUCTION

The macroscopical failure of fiber reinforced composites is due to the accumulation of local failure processes such as fiber breakage, matrix and interface failure. All three elementary failure processes can arise in any combination, depending on the specific inhomogeneities and the specific strengths of the components. Besides the strength and fracture toughness of fiber and matrix, the bonding between fiber and matrix has an important influence on the elementary failure processes and, as a result, on the damage tolerance of the composite material. Accordingly, the key to the understanding of the damage tolerance of fiber reinforced composites lies in the understanding of the role of the interface. A key parameter for the characterisation of the interface with regard to the macroscopic fracture toughness is the critical energy release rate of the interface, as measured with micromechanical tests, for example pull-out tests [1, 2]. In addition, interfacial friction developing in the debonded zones has a remarkable influence on the energy absorption. Since the local failure processes cannot be studied experimentally, model studies are performed based on the finite element method in order to evaluate the possible fracture processes. To this end, the energy release rate arising in different failure processes - pure fiber break or fiber break accompanied by a simultaneous matrix crack followed by an interface crack - is calculated in terms of parametric studies. This

is done by means of finite analyses in a way similar to the fracture mechanical analyses used by several authors in the last years, mainly applied to micromechanical tests [3-7]. The influence of initial thermal stresses arising in case of a thermoplastic matrix as well as the influence of interfacial friction is studied. Furthermore, the fiber type - glass and carbon fibers - as well as the fiber volume fraction is varied. In order to compare the results for different fibers and crack patterns, the crack propagation is analysed under a fixed external load. All calculations presented in this paper should be understood as parametric studies, which allow an estimation of the main parameters influencing local failure. They cannot cover the full complexity of the reality.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The studies are performed using an idealised model, which is similar to a fragmentation test model. It consists of a single fiber embedded in a matrix cylinder (fig. 1a). In case of composite material, a three phase model is used, consisting of fiber and matrix which is surrounded by a cylindrical shell of an equivalent composite material. The model is axisymmetrical and a further plane symmetry (in axial direction) is assumed in the plane of the fiber break. The mesh is strongly refined in the neighbourhood of the fiber break because of the high stress concentrations encountered here (fig. 1b). The analysis is performed in terms of an incremental procedure. The radial fiber and matrix cracks are realised by a solution of boundary conditions. The interfacial crack propagation is realised by successively solving the links between the adjacent fiber and matrix elements along the interface. The crack increments vary between $r_f/30$ and $r_f/10$, that is $1/6 \mu\text{m}$ and $1/2 \mu\text{m}$. In order to prevent interpenetration of the crack faces and to take into account interfacial friction after debonding, a contact algorithm is used. The fiber diameter is normalised to $10 \mu\text{m}$. The length of the model system is two times l_{sys} with $l_{\text{sys}} = 400 \mu\text{m}$, the radius r_{sys} is $100 \mu\text{m}$. The breakage of the fiber is simulated with or without simultaneously developing radial matrix or interface cracks of different lengths. After total fiber break interface cracks develop propagating up to a length of four fiber radii ($20 \mu\text{m}$).

Fig. 1: a) Sketch of the model system, b) finite element mesh

The materials under consideration are a polycarbonate matrix and glass or carbon fibers. The study is limited to linear elastic material behaviour, which limits the analysis to moderate deformations of the matrix. Matrix and glass fibers are assumed to be isotropic, while the carbon fibers are modeled as transversely isotropic (table 1).

Table 1 Elastic and thermal constants of fibers and matrix
(a = axial direction, t = transversal direction)

matrix (polycarbonate) isotropic	E-glass fiber isotropic	HM-carbon fiber transversely isotropic
$E = 2300 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$E = 73500 \text{ N/mm}^2$	$E_a = 405000 \text{ N/mm}^2$
$\nu = 0.38$	$\nu = 0.18$	$E_t = 8600 \text{ N/mm}^2$
		$G_{at} = 13700 \text{ N/mm}^2$
		$\nu_{at} = 0.35$
		$\nu_{tt} = 0.53$
$\alpha_T = 70 \text{ E}^{-6} \text{ K}$	$\alpha_T = 4.5 \text{ E}^{-6} \text{ K}$	$\alpha_{Ta} = -1.4 \text{ E}^{-6} \text{ K}$
		$\alpha_{Tt} = 12.0 \text{ E}^{-6} \text{ K}$

RELEASED ENERGY DURING FIBER BREAKAGE AND DEBONDING

One of the most likely elementary failure processes is the breakage of the fiber starting at a microdefect at the fiber surface. Several situations are conceivable. i) The fiber breakage takes place without matrix or interface cracks. After total fiber break, an interface crack develops. ii). Simultaneously with the propagation of the fiber crack, a radial matrix crack develops. The two most essential parameters characterising the failure process are the energy released by the different processes as well as the corresponding energy release rate. These are calculated for several crack combinations.

Fiber Break followed by an Interface Crack

In the first case, the pure breakage of the fiber without a matrix crack followed by an interface crack is studied. Thermal and frictional stresses are not taken into account at this point. The crack starts at the fiber surface and propagates towards the center of the fiber (figs. 2a, 2b). In fig. 3 the total energy released during crack propagation is plotted versus a coordinate corresponding to the crack length. The negative values of **a** correspond to the fiber break, which starts at **a** = -5 μm (fiber surface) and ends at **a** = 0 μm (center of the fiber). The interface crack starts at **a** = 0 and propagates up to a length of 4 fiber radii, i.e. **a** = 20 μm . This is, the crack length coordinate **a** should not be taken for the total crack length.

Fig. 2: Sketch of crack patterns a) pure fiber crack b) interface crack after fiber break

The energy released during fiber crack increases steeply with growing crack length (fig. 3), especially when the crack approaches the center of the fiber ($a \rightarrow 0$). When the interfacial debonding starts after total fiber breakage, a very large portion of strain energy is released. With further interfacial crack propagation, the process of energy release slows down and the trace of the total released energy becomes almost linear.

Fig. 3: Released energy during fiber and interface crack - glass fiber, $\mu=0$, $\Delta T=0$

The large amount of energy released during a very short crack length at the initiation of the interface crack may be surprising at a first glance. However, this is due to the fact that, per definition, the fiber surface is still perfectly bonded to the matrix after fiber break (fig. 4a). The matrix in the plane of the fiber break, on the other hand, cannot move in the axial direction, since it is fixed at the plane of symmetry, resulting in extremely high stresses near the interface. With other words, the fiber surface nodes are still connected via the matrix. This link is removed, when the interface crack starts (fig. 4b). As a result, the fiber end can retract and the region around the interface is significantly unloaded, releasing a large amount of strain energy.

Fig. 4: Sketch of deformation a) fiber break, full bonding b) fiber break, interface crack c) fiber break, matrix crack

While the crack runs from the surface to the center of the fiber, the crack area increment decreases. As a result, the energy release rate increases dramatically during crack extension (fig. 5). Since the increment of the crack area tends to zero at the center of the fiber, the energy release rate has a singularity at this point. The fast growing energy release rate indicates that the fracture process of the fiber is unstable, which is not questioned. Contrary to the fiber crack, the crack area increment of the interface crack is constant. According to the course of the released energy, the energy release rate is extremely high at the beginning of the interface crack (fig. 5). It decreases very steeply during interfacial crack extension. Within a crack length of about one fiber radius, the energy release rate becomes approximately constant at a comparatively low level. The large amount of strain energy released during fiber fracture is much higher than the work necessary to break the fiber. Accordingly, an isolated fiber break without a matrix or interface crack is not very likely. This effect can often be observed in

fragmentation tests, where at least small matrix cracks are encountered at fiber breaks. On the other hand, the extremely high energy release rate at the initiation of the interface crack indicates an unstable crack propagation also in that phase.

Fig. 5: Energy release rate during fiber and interface crack - glass fiber, $\mu=0$, $\Delta T=0$

Fiber Break with simultaneous Matrix Crack followed by Interface Crack

In the second study, a penny-shaped matrix crack is assumed to develop simultaneously with the fiber crack perpendicular to the fiber surface. Different lengths of matrix cracks are investigated, e.g. one fiber radius, $1/3$ and $1/30$ fiber radius (figs. 6a, 6b). The energy released during crack propagation versus the crack length coordinate is shown in fig. 7. In order to achieve a better comparability of the results for different matrix cracks, the lengths of the simultaneous matrix cracks are not included in the crack length coordinate a . That is, the same convention is used as in case of the pure fiber break (figs. 3, 5).

Fig. 6: Sketch of crack patterns a) fiber crack with simultaneous matrix crack
b) interface crack after fiber break and matrix crack

It is not surprising that the amount of released energy is increased when a matrix crack develops simultaneously with the fiber crack (fig. 7). However, the large amount of energy, which is released even by a very short matrix crack ($a_m = r_f / 30$) is surprising. The reason of that effect is similar to that arising at the initiation of the interface crack, described in the preceding section. As a result of the matrix crack, the highly stressed matrix next to the interface undergoes a large displacement. This results in an overproportional unloading of the region of the fiber near the interface (fig. 4c). Accordingly, the energy released at the initiation of the interface crack is strongly decreased in case of a matrix crack.

In each case, the slope of the released energy strongly increases when the crack approaches the center of the fiber, resulting in an extremely high energy release rate. The slope of the energy released by the interface crack after total fiber breakage, is significantly different for the various matrix crack lengths. While in case of no matrix crack, a jump of energy was encountered, the slope diminishes significantly with the length of the matrix crack. For the rather long matrix cracks of one third and one fiber radius, the slope is even ascending in the beginning if the interface crack. With growing interface crack length, all traces approach the same slope. In addition, the large differences of the released energy at the beginning of the interface crack level off.

Fig. 7: Released energy during fiber and interface crack with simultaneous matrix cracks, glass fiber, $\mu = 0$, $\Delta T = 0$, $a_m =$ length of radial matrix crack, fiber radius $r_f = 5 \mu\text{m}$

According to the course of the released energy, the energy release rate decreases steeply from a maximum after fiber break in case of no or short matrix cracks. However, in case of the larger matrix cracks ($r_f/3$ and r_f) the energy release rate is very low at the onset of the interface crack and increases during the first phase of the crack. With growing interfacial crack length, all traces approach the same level.

Fig. 8: Energy release rate during fiber and interface crack with simultaneous matrix cracks, glass fiber, $\mu = 0$, $\Delta T = 0$, $a_m =$ length of radial matrix crack, fiber radius $r_f = 5 \mu\text{m}$

INFLUENCE OF THERMAL STRESSES, INTERFACIAL FRICTION AND FIBER TYPE ON THE ENERGY RELEASE RATE

Interfacial friction is an important factor concerning the energy absorption during failure, if debonding occurs. The energy release rate for an interface crack developing after fiber breakage for various coefficients of friction is plotted in figure 9 for a glass fiber system. For better visibility, the scale has been changed. In order to show the limits, zero friction as well as perfect friction is taken into account. The dissipation process results in a significant reduction of the energy release rate, even though thermal stresses are not taken into account in this analysis. Especially in the zone of steep decrease, that is at the beginning of the interface crack, the reduction is extremely high. This is due to the fact that the ability of the fiber to relieve is restrained. In case of perfect friction, the energy release rate would be reduced by about more than 60% at a crack length of 4 fiber radii (20 μm) compared with zero friction.

Fig. 9: Energy release rate for carbon fiber system, variation of friction coefficient

In case of a carbon fiber, the displacement applied to the axial boundaries of the model is reduced according to the higher stiffness of the carbon fiber. The energy release rate is much lower compared with the glass fiber system (fig. 10) as a result of the higher fiber stiffness. The influence of friction is generally similar for both fiber types, even though it is somewhat lower in case of a carbon compared with the glass fiber.

Fig. 10: Energy release rate for carbon fiber system, variation of friction coefficient

The thermal stresses enhance the compressive stresses in the interface and, in turn, enlarge the work of friction after debonding. The energy release rates of the glass and carbon fiber system are shown in fig. 11 for perfect friction. For both, glass and carbon fibers, the enlarged energy dissipation reduces the energy release rate significantly, this is, by about one third in case of the glass fiber and one quarter in case of the carbon fiber. The high amount of the energy dissipated due to friction as a result of thermal stresses shows that, even though a good adhesion is necessary to achieve a stiff composite with high strength, a high damage tolerance, on the other hand, requires extensive debonding in combination with interfacial friction.

Fig. 11: Energy release rate for glass and carbon fiber system, influence of thermal stresses

The calculations presented so far are performed for a single fiber. Now, the influence of the fiber volume fraction is studied. To this end, the elementary cell consisting of one fiber embedded in a matrix cylinder representing the fiber volume fraction, is surrounded by a cylindrical shell of equivalent composite material. Three fiber volume fractions are considered: 8%, 25% and 51% Due to the increased stiffness of the surrounding material, the retraction of the matrix in the vicinity of the fiber break is restrained. As a result, the energy released by the interface crack is significantly reduced (fig. 12). Especially during the first phase of the interface crack, the reduction is very high. In case of a high fiber volume fraction (51%), the plateau of the energy release rate is reached within a crack length of only one fiber radius.

Fig. 12: Energy release rate for a glass fiber system, variation of fiber volume fraction

CONCLUSIONS

The numerical analyses of the elementary failure processes have shown that the energy dissipation by friction after debonding is an essential factor concerning the damage tolerance of a composite. It comes out that initial thermal stresses or, in case of thermosetting matrices, curing stresses, have to be taken into account in a theoretical or numerical analysis of the failure processes order to get a reasonable estimation of the fracture toughness. A further result, which is of relevance also for the evaluation of fragmentation tests, is the fact that the process of fiber fracture probably does not occur isolated but is accompanied either by matrix or interface cracks. The analysis presented here, which is based on linear elasticity, has to be extended by taking into account nonlinear and time dependent material behaviour.

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